

GT2023-103023

ON THE DEMONSTRATION OF A HUMID COMBUSTION SYSTEM PERFORMING FLEXIBLE FUEL-SWITCH FROM PURE HYDROGEN TO NATURAL GAS WITH ULTRA-LOW NO_x EMISSIONS

Simeon Dybe^{1,*}, Muhammad Yasir¹, Felix Güthe²,
Reddy Alemela², Michael Bartlett², Bruno Schuermanns¹, Christian Oliver Paschereit¹

¹Chair of Fluid Dynamics, Technische Universität Berlin, 10623 Berlin, Germany

²Phoenix BioPower, 11428 Stockholm, Sweden

ABSTRACT

To fight global warming the European Union formulated the objective of completely decarbonising the energy sector, stimulating the advent of unconventional fuels and the adaptation of the corresponding energy infrastructure. The decarbonisation strategy identified hydrogen to play a key role as an energy storage medium, making systems capable of pure hydrogen operation essential.

This requirement can be fulfilled with humid power cycles which offer additional advantages such as highly efficient and fuel-flexible operation with low emissions. As an integral part of such a cycle, a humid combustion system was presented previously showing promising results with respect to complete combustion with low emissions for a variety of fuels.

The current work introduces an upgraded version of that combustion system. The new Double Swirler system is capable of stable and safe combustion of low calorific value bio-syngas surrogate, hydrogen, and natural gas, from dry to steam-rich conditions within the required pressure drops. The inclusion of dry operation of the system can benefit the start-up procedure of the humid cycle.

The combustor's fuel switching performance is demonstrated by a fast fuel switch at full load from pure hydrogen to pure natural gas and vice versa, while maintaining a stable performance with low NO_x-emissions at otherwise constant operation parameters.

Keywords: Humid combustion, MILD-Combustion, Fuel-flexibility, Hydrogen combustion, Syngas combustion, Emissions, Double Swirler

1. INTRODUCTION

The primary measure against the climate change is to reduce man-made greenhouse gas emissions. The European Green Deal targets net-zero emission until the year 2050 [1]. The consequent phase-out of fossil fuels stimulated the advent of alternative fuels,

most notably hydrogen (H₂) as one future pillar of the energy storage system [2]. Its efficient conversion to power and heat requires systems capable of operating with 100% H₂. To reach that goal, current development efforts aim at either retrofitting existing gas turbines to include H₂ as fuel, blending it with natural gas (NG), or developing novel combustion technologies capable of H₂ or fuel-flexible operation.

As is generally known, including H₂ into the existing range of gas turbine fuels is a major challenge due to its relatively high reactive nature, which affects all combustion and engine operation aspects. The ETN report [3] summarizes the primary challenges with fuel-flexible NG/H₂-combustion as follows: auto-ignition, flashback, thermo-acoustic, NO_x-emission, operation within acceptable pressure loss, and component cooling. In the early phase of combustor design, especially flashback, blowout and NO_x-emission are primary concerns.

The increased risk of flashback for fuels with high-H₂ content is rooted in augmented flame speeds and reduced ignition times compared to NG-combustion. These properties have been analyzed in numerous studies both experimentally and numerically [4, 5].

The ratio of laminar flame speed of non-preheated H₂/air and NG/air mixtures under atmospheric and stoichiometric conditions is approximately 6, with H₂/air flame speed of 2.1 m/s and NG/air flame speed of 0.35 m/s [6]. This ratio increases from ambient (NPT) to engine conditions. Simulations by Mohammad et al. [7] at elevated pressure (23 atm) and preheat temperature (793 K) yield a ratio of approximately 10. Numerical investigations conducted by Brower et al. [8] with CH₄/H₂/air blends show that the main effect of H₂ addition on the laminar flame speed for lean mixtures at engine conditions (25atm, 753K) occurs at high H₂ contents. The laminar flame speed doubles when increasing the H₂ content from 0 to 70vol%, and further triples from 70 to 100vol%. The non-linear increase thus makes it exceedingly challenging to operate engines at high-H₂ contents.

Petersen et al. [9] experimentally studied ignition delay times

*Corresponding author: dybe@tu-berlin.de

of CH₄/H₂/air mixtures at pressures close to 21 atm, temperatures from 1141 K to 1553 K, and an equivalence ratio of 0.5. They found that the ignition delay time of fuel blends with a H₂ content of 20% is 3 times lower compared to CH₄/air mixtures, and even 10 times lower at 40vol% H₂.

In their simulations, Brower et al. [8] studied ignition delay times as a function of pressure for CH₄/H₂/air blends at engine conditions (1100K, $\Phi=0.7$). At ambient pressure, the ignition delay time of H₂/air is three orders of magnitudes lower than that of a CH₄/air. When increasing the pressure from 1 to 12 atm, the ignition delay time of the CH₄/air mixture decreases exponentially by over an order of magnitude. However, an inverse behaviour was identified for the H₂/air mixture. Its ignition delay time increased over the same pressure range by roughly one order of magnitude with a non-monotonous growth rate.

Further, operation under emission compliance is a key objective for engine design. According to [3], substituting NG with H₂ can lead to increased NO_x-emission associated with higher flame temperatures.

Consequently, to realize sustainable operation on the full H₂/NG fuel range requires careful design of the engine. Accordingly, gas turbine manufacturers are currently exploring the possibilities of adapting their NG-fueled gas turbines.

Siemens demonstrated H₂/NG operation of up to 60vol% H₂ on their 5000F and 8000H under full pressure with the goal of fully flexible operation covering the entire H₂/NG range until 2030 [10]. They further introduced their work on the ACE (Advanced Combustion System for high Efficiency) combustion system, a jet stabilized main burner to support operation with higher H₂ loads, tested on a SGT6-9000HL with up to 50vol% H₂ [11]. Engines equipped with DLE (Dry Low Emission) system are capable of operating with up to 60vol% H₂ [3].

MAN introduced a flow conditioner for flashback resistance to a small-sized engine MGT6000 with a standard burner and thus achieved an increase from 25vol% H₂ to up to 45vol% at elevated pressure and 93vol% at atmospheric pressure under emission compliance [12].

GE Research Center conducted tests with their dry low NO_x burner with an advanced mixer at elevated pressure. Operation at 100% H₂ was achieved with high NO_x-emission at elevated temperatures with a 4% pressure loss [7]. At a flame temperature of 1935 K, addition of up to 20vol% H₂ to a NG/air combustion shows a negligible effect on NO_x-emission. However, by further increasing the H₂ content to up to 100vol% leads to a significant NO_x increase of >1000%.

Kawasaki in cooperation with RWTH Aachen developed a novel multi-nozzle combustor and powered a 2MW M1A-17 gas turbine co-generation system in a long-term study with 100% H₂ at full load [13].

In addition to retrofitting existing systems, the transition of the power sector towards 100% H₂ can be supported by novel cycle technologies such as humid cycles and oxyfuel combustion.

Detailed investigation on the effect of steam on the combustion has been carried out by Göke [14], using a swirl premix combustor fired with H₂/NG/N₂/air blends. The study comprises an analysis of the emission behaviour and flame stability under steam-rich conditions. Increasing the steam content sup-

presses the NO_x-formation via the thermal pathway and thus reduces overall NO_x-emission. At the same time, the prompt NO_x-pathway gains in importance. However, this pathway is of no importance for H₂ combustion. For otherwise constant combustion parameters, steam addition shifts the blowout-limit to higher equivalence ratios. Under humid conditions and using large recirculation zones the combustion regime is changing into the Moderate or Intense Low oxygen Dilution (MILD) region [15, 16], which is described to favour low NO_x emissions.

Zero-emission oxyfuel H₂ combustion tests at atmospheric pressure were conducted at TU Berlin [17]. The steam which would act as working fluid in the power cycle was passed through two modular swirlers to generate a recirculation zone in the combustion chamber for flame stabilization. The flame behaviour and combustion efficiency were investigated as a function of different combustion parameters, such as swirl number, swirler configuration and steam dilution. High efficiency combustion could be achieved, however, without reaching complete conversion to pure H₂O in the exhaust.

The current work aims at the development of a combustion system for humid power cycles with fuel-flexible operation. Previously, a system was introduced capable of combustion with 100% NG, H₂ as well as fuel surrogate representing syngas from biomass [18, 19]. In the following results, an optimised combustor design is presented which further extends the operation range of the combustor. The operation range now spans from dry up to steam-rich conditions, while enabling operation within the required pressure loss (around 3%). Furthermore, at constant air and steam flowrates, a fuel switch from 100% H₂ to 100% NG and back is demonstrated, proving fuel-flexible operation capability.

2. INTRODUCTION OF THE NOVEL COMBUSTION SYSTEM

This section describes the technical requirements for a combustor operating in a fuel-flexible humid combustion cycle followed by a description of the novel combustion concept.

2.1 SYSTEM REQUIREMENTS

The current study is part of a project which aims for design and experimental validation of a combustion system integrated in a fuel-flexible humid power cycle such as the TopCycle [20].

Humid power cycles make efficient use of steam addition, which can be injected at several locations throughout the cycle. Usually, steam is supplied upstream of, or directly into, the combustion chamber, a measure initially introduced to mitigate NO_x-emission. Restraining the NO_x-formation is a major aspect of steam's influence on combustion chemistry, which generally can be broken down in a chemical and physical interaction. Most notably, steam presence reduces flame temperatures and hotspots. Further, it affects reaction pathways, both by directly participating in the reactions and reducing radical fractions [21].

Apart from its beneficial effect on NO_x-formation, however, these effects also influence other combustion properties. For instance, steam addition leads to reduced volumetric heating values and reduced reactivity expressed as reduced flame speed or increased extinction times. The steam-induced reactivity reduction

FIGURE 1: ATMOSPHERIC COMBUSTION TEST RIG WITH DOUBLE SWIRLER CONCEPT CONFIGURATION

can be partly compensated by decreasing the combustion air flow, thus operating the system closer to the stoichiometric condition. Consequently, air compression costs can be reduced, while increasing flame temperature and reactivity, altogether improving the power cycle efficiency. Furthermore, high NO_x -emission associated with increased equivalence ratio and thus flame temperature are suppressed by the above mentioned influence of steam on the combustion chemistry.

Humid combustion can be utilized to extend the operation range of power cycles firing high reactive fuels such as H_2 . Steam addition reduces flame temperature, flame speed and combustion reactivity, consequently improving the flashback safety. For the same reason, the risk of blowout is increased for less reactive fuels at lower flame temperatures compared to dry combustion.

The TopCycle, an advanced version of a humid power cycle, features operation over a large fuel spectrum extending from high-reactive H_2 to low-reactive syngas from biomass or NG in a steam-rich atmosphere.

The TopCycle makes efficient use of the integration of a gasifier supplying the cycle with syngas generated from biomass at high pressures and after passing a hot gas filter. Characteristically, a large share of these gasifier output gases are inert gases and steam. Thus, they feature very low lower heating values (LHV) relative to H_2 and NG. Additionally, their composition and outlet temperature are sensitive to the gasifier's operating conditions and feedstock and therefore are subjected to a certain volatility. During plant operation the gasifier output is directly supplied to the combustor, therefore the combustion system must ensure safe operation over the entire range of the resulting gas composition. For stable operation under emission compliance, the fuel-flexible humid combustion system must be carefully designed for combustion over the described fuel reactivity range.

As an initial approach, stable humid fuel-flexible combustion was demonstrated employing a premix combustor developed at TU Berlin at ultra-low NO_x and CO emissions [18, 19]. The combustor's cylindrical swirler features high swirl numbers constituting a strong and stable recirculation zone in the combustion chamber. This benefits flame stabilisation of low-reactive fuels such as surrogate syngas and NG and also enabled H_2 combustion, however, with flashback at lower steam ratios. Additionally, pressure losses were relatively high at high flow velocities.

2.2 DOUBLE SWIRLER CONCEPT

Adapted from the initial burner concept and geometry, the upgraded burner version introduced in this work - the Double Swirler - was developed based on the previous experimental and numerical test results. The primary scope of the novel design was to ensure a large operation window for fuel-flexible humid operation including 100% NG, 100% H_2 as well as syngas from biomass as fuels.

A special focus was laid on the burner's fuel switching ability to allow for safe and fast transition from operation with pure NG to pure H_2 and back. As was shown previously, combustion with syngas comprising typical gasifier output compositions exhibit improved flame stability compared to humid NG-flames, possibly due to its elevated H_2 content. Thus, a safe transition to syngas is also implied in a NG/ H_2 -switch.

Given the importance of H_2 combustion, a design objective of the novel burner concept was improved flashback resistance, with the goal of safe H_2 operation even under dry conditions. At the same time, the design aimed at a pressure loss reduction over the burner compared to the initial approach.

According to the intended field of application, a special focus was laid on the combustion of syngas from biomass. Since syngas produced with a gasifier may contain condensable substances, such as higher hydrocarbons (tars), the design should include measures against fouling. Finally, a primary design target was to achieve ultra-low emissions over the entire fuel-flexible operating envelope.

The novel combustion system follows the approach of swirler-stabilised fuel-flexible humid combustion as described above (Section 2.1). The new concept consists of two swirlers. Fuel and steam are supplied through the upstream (us) swirler, and air through the subsequent downstream (ds) swirler (Fig. 1). The air can also be humidified if required for the cycle operation.

In the previous concept, premix combustion was used to create a homogeneous fuel distribution, thus preventing the formation of regions of incomplete combustion and thus high CO emissions. However, stable combustion with a fuel comprising a very low LHV was demonstrated successfully with CO values well below the legal limit, thus allowing to deviate from the fully-premix approach. Regarding NO_x -emissions, the fuel/air unmixedness becomes less relevant under humid conditions [14].

The Double Swirler concept leads to improved flashback stability. Combustibles and air are introduced just upstream of the combustion chamber and stay relatively unmixed throughout the mixing tube. Furthermore, an increased axial momentum is introduced inside the mixing tube, which proved beneficial for the flashback resistance [22].

To counteract the relative unmixedness in the mixing tube, the swirlers are designed such that a large swirl number is produced over the entire desired operation window, even at comparably low flows (dry combustion). This leads to the formation of a stable and strong recirculation zone in the combustion chamber and hence flame stability, enhanced mixing and a high combustion efficiency.

Besides flashback resistance, feeding the inflow into the combustion chamber from two separate swirlers shows advantageous pressure loss behaviour, since the flow area is increased compared

to the previous concept.

Furthermore, when mixing air and fuel at lower air pre-heat temperatures, the mixing temperature can fall below the tar's dew point. Consequently, this would increase the risk of condensation and thus fouling. In the novel Double Swirler concept, air and fuel are mixed directly upstream of the combustion chamber, which limits the region affected by tar fouling just to the mixing tube.

This work is a report on the current project phase, which fundamentally investigates the performance of the novel Double Swirler concept. This comprises the assessment of the operation envelope, emission behaviour and fuel switch ability under atmospheric pressure conditions. In the subsequent development phases the Double Swirler concept will be evaluated at elevated pressure conditions and finally integrated in an engine prototype. Alongside experimental validation, the Double Swirler performance is investigated by means of reactive LES-simulation [16].

3. METHODOLOGY

This section introduces the atmospheric combustion test rig, the numerical analysis tools, used operation parameters, and gives an overview of the measurement range of the presented data.

3.1 Atmospheric combustion test rig

The novel burner design was experimentally characterized at TU Berlin under atmospheric pressure. A schematic of the test rig is presented in Fig. 1. Superheated steam heated up to 500°C and fuel at ambient temperature were mixed perfectly upstream and fed through the upstream swirler. Preheated air at a temperature of up to 650°C was injected through the downstream swirler. Temperature and static pressure were measured at the inlet of both the swirlers.

Air and fuel were guided through a mixing tube into the combustion chamber. Typically, for swirling flows undergoing an abrupt area expansion, a central recirculation zone is anchored in the cylindrical quartz glass combustion chamber (D=200 mm, L=300 mm). At its base plate, the static pressure was measured. In the subsequent exhaust section, an emission sample was extracted directly after the combustion chamber and exhaust temperatures were measured at the central axis of the flow along the exhaust tube.

All the temperature measurements were conducted using type K thermocouples. The static pressures were taken with differential pressure sensors of type IDM341 from ICS-Schneider, which feature an error of $\leq 1\%$ of the full-scale output and a measurement range of 0 to 100 mbar. Gas mass flowrates (air, H₂, NG, N₂) were measured using Coriolis mass flow meters from Endress+Hauser, while the steam mass flowrate was assessed with a swirl flow meter from ABB. The measurement error of all flow meter devices is $\leq \pm 0.5\%$ of the measured value. A simple USB camera from Sipro was used for flame images in the visible spectrum. The OH^{*}-chemiluminescence of the flame was recorded with an image-intensified CCD camera from LaVision equipped with an UV-transmissive lens (f/3.8, f = 78 mm). Additionally, the lens was equipped with an interference filter transmissive between 295 and 340 nm. For each operation point a total of 450 frames at a frequency of 5 frames per second were recorded.

TABLE 1: PARAMETERS USED IN THE EXPERIMENTS.

Parameter	Value
Pressure	Atmospheric
Fuels	H ₂ , Natural gas, Surrogate syngas
Surrogate syngas fuel composition H ₂ /NG/N ₂ (vol%)	17 / 17 / 66
Burner inlet temperature (°C)	300
Thermal power P _{th} (kW)	100
Equivalence ratio ϕ (-)	0.6 - 0.9
Steam ratio Ω (-)	0-0.5
Adiabatic flame temperature (K)	1563 (humid) - 2285 (dry)

During the tests, a continuous emission measurement was performed by extracting a gas sample from the exhaust flow. Via a heated hose pipe the sample was fed into a cooled steam trap to remove condensate, before it was analyzed for emission concentrations of unburned hydrocarbons (UHC), NO_x, CO, O₂, and CO₂ on a dry basis. CO and CO₂ were assessed based on their absorption behaviour. The NO_x-analyzer operates with chemiluminescence measurements. The analyzer further distinguished between NO and NO₂. O₂ was quantified based on the molecule's paramagnetic characteristic. The measurement error of the NO_x-measurement is $< 1.4\%$ of the full-scale output (0-120 ppm), that of O₂ $< 0.75\%$ (0-25%), and that for CO $< 1.1\%$ (range: 0-200ppm).

Hydrogen and nitrogen were supplied from gas bottles (purity 99.9 %) and natural gas from the public grid. Formerly, the NG composition in the public grid was composed of CH₄ almost exclusively. The current shift in the gas supply market has led to a reduction of the CH₄ content, even if it is still the most dominant contributor to the NG composition. The change in NG composition introduces an uncertainty to all calculated values, since in this study NG is represented by CH₄. We expect that this assumption captures the here demonstrated combustion effects still sufficiently well, since the difference of NG to CH₄ is relatively small especially when compared to the full fuel range (100% H₂ to 100% NG).

3.2 OPERATION PARAMETERS

3.2.1 Equivalence ratio. Equivalence ratio is defined as a given fuel to air ratio normalized by fuel to air ratio at stoichiometric condition and it is the reciprocal of the air excess number λ :

$$\phi = \frac{\dot{m}_{fuel}}{\dot{m}_{air}} \Big|_{st} = \frac{1}{\lambda} \quad (1)$$

3.2.2 Steam ratio. Steam ratio is defined as mass flowrate of steam divided by mass flowrate of air:

$$\Omega = \frac{\dot{m}_{H_2O}}{\dot{m}_{air}} \quad (2)$$

FIGURE 2: DOUBLE SWIRLER OPERATION ENVELOPE FOR HYDROGEN (H₂), NATURAL GAS (NG) AND SUROGATE SYNGAS FLAMES, $T_{IN}=300^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P=1\text{ATM}$, $P_{th}=100\text{KW}$

3.2.3 Pressure loss coefficient. The pressure loss coefficient ζ is defined as the pressure drop Δp along a streamline normalized with the volume-specific axial kinetic energy

$$\zeta = 2 \frac{\Delta p}{\rho u^2} = 2 \frac{\rho A^2 \Delta p}{\dot{m}^2} \quad (3)$$

with the mean axial velocity u , mass flowrate \dot{m} , effective flow area A and the density ρ of the gas mixture.

3.2.4 Adiabatic flame temperature. Adiabatic flame temperatures are computed from experimentally obtained mass flows and temperatures with Cantera's [23] equilibrium calculation on the basis of the FFCM-1 mechanism [24].

3.2.5 Emission correction. The emission correction for fuel variations between H₂ and NG has recently been a topic of discussion as pointed out in several publications [25–28]. Similar approaches converge to the agreement that the change in exhaust gas volume for varying fuels impacts correction with reference to 15% O₂ and therefore is misleading. Compared to hydrocarbon flames, high hydrogen fuels produce almost 40% less volume (and thus higher concentration) for the same thermal energy, consequently penalizing the hydrogen application using the 15%O₂ correction. Hence, in the current work the emission data are presented in raw ppm values or corrected to mass per energy (net thermal input). This correction can be obtained by expressing the emissions in mass (g(NO₂) for NO_x), per volume (mg/Nm³) and applying the fuel factor S (Nm³/MJ). Procedures to determine the fuel factor are given in the standard ISO-16911 and are described in the Appendix A.

3.3 Measurement parameters

For the purpose of experimental validation, the burner is operated at atmospheric pressure. All operating parameters are scaled accordingly, resulting in a baseload thermal power of $P_{th}=100\text{ kW}$.

FIGURE 3: FLAME IMAGES IN THE VISIBLE SPECTRUM AND TIME-AVERAGED OH*-IMAGES FOR H₂ AND NG FLAMES FOR STEAM RATIO $\Omega=0$ AND HIGH Ω , POINTS 1-4 CORRESPONDING TO FIG. 2

Following the operation concept of the TopCycle, combustion under steam-rich conditions is partly compensated by operation close to the stoichiometric condition, resulting in equivalence ratios for the presented cases in the range of $\Phi=0.6-0.9$.

The steam flowrate can be controlled between 15-60 kg/h due to the limitations of the swirl flow meter installed in the steam line. Therefore, the rig was operated at conditions corresponding to a steam ratio Ω of zero and approximately in the range of 0.1-0.5.

The combustor inlet temperature was maintained close to 300°C for all test cases.

4. RESULTS

In the following, a general overview on the burner's stability map is presented. Subsequently, the combustor's pressure loss is discussed. Finally, a H₂/NG fuel switch is demonstrated.

4.1 Operation envelope

Figure 2 gives an overview of the Double Swirler's operation range. The measured points are depicted in the Φ - Ω space, where each marker represents a stable flame. In this figure, the stability behaviour of the tested fuel types (\times H₂, \circ NG, \diamond Syngas) is investigated. All other combustion parameters were kept constant in accordance with Tab. 3 ($T_{in}=300^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P_{th}=100\text{ kW}$).

The Double Swirler's operating behaviour was tested primarily close to its design point, leading to the majority of the tested points located around $\Phi = 0.8$ and $\Omega = 0.3$.

Increasing the steam content for a constant equivalence ratio leads to blowout for NG and syngas flames. As described above, increasing the steam content affects the combustion chemistry in multiple ways, most notably by decreasing the flame temperature and reducing the radical pool. Consequently, the reactivity of the combusted mixture is decreased until blowout. It can be seen, that syngas flames can withstand blowout at higher steam ratios compared to humid NG flames. This can be ascribed to the syngas' elevated H₂ content, since already small H₂ contents have a beneficial effect on flame stability [29]. A blowout induced by

FIGURE 4: ABSOLUTE NO_x-EMISSION OVER STEAM RATIO Ω FOR A NG ($\Phi=0.9$) AND A H₂-FLAME ($\Phi=0.7$), $T_{in}=300^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P_{th}=100\text{KW}$; EMISSION AT $\Omega=0$ ONLY FOR DEMONSTRATION PURPOSE

increasing the steam flowrate was technically unfeasible for H₂-flames under baseload conditions, since the H₂-flames resisted blowout at the maximal available steam flow.

Reducing the steam content to $\Omega = 0$, and thus increasing the mixture's reactivity and flame temperature, increases the risk of flashback. The Double Swirler's combustion behaviour at dry conditions was investigated with H₂/air at $\Phi=0.7$ and NG/air at $\Phi=0.9$. Stable combustion was realized for both fuel types. Hereby, no immediate damage to the burner hardware was detected.

Stable combustion with a surrogate syngas fuel was demonstrated for $\Phi=0.8$ and 0.9 under humid conditions. In summary, the Double Swirler concept is capable of realizing stable combustion for various fuel types both under dry and humid conditions.

4.2 Effect of steam ratio

4.2.1 Flame images. Figure 3 presents flame image snapshots in the visible range and line-of-sight time-averaged OH* chemiluminescence for H₂ and NG combustion on both borders of the before presented operation envelope. The corresponding operation points are marked on the operation map (Fig. 2). No filter was applied to the camera in the visible spectrum. The time-averaged, line-of-sight OH*-images are corrected to the maximum OH*-intensity of each image. Flow direction is from bottom to top.

On the left side, both dry NG and H₂ are V-type flames typical for dry, swirl-stabilized combustion. In the visible range, the dry NG-flame (point 1) is emitting its typical blue light. In contrast, the dry H₂-flame (point 3) is almost invisible and emits only a very weak bluish radiation. The bluish color may stem from the broadband continuum overlaid with fine spectral structures [30]. In both cases, the quartz glass glows yellow owing to the high temperature blackbody radiation.

The main heat release zones associated with increased OH*-presence are located in similar regions for both fuels, with the

FIGURE 5: ABSOLUTE PRESSURE LOSS OVER THE UPSTREAM (US) SWIRLER AND THE DOWNSTREAM (DS) SWIRLER AS A FUNCTION OF STEAM RATIO Ω FOR A NG ($\Phi=0.9$) AND A H₂-FLAME ($\Phi=0.7$), $T_{in}=300^{\circ}$, $P_{th}=100\text{KW}$

flame root extending to the mixing tube.

At an elevated steam ratio, the humid H₂-flame (point 4) again emits a weak blue light. In contrast to the dry combustion case, the glow of the quartz glass is significantly reduced. The increased steam content decreases the flame temperature and also cools the glass walls. The main heat release zone is more compact compared to the dry case and located directly downstream of the outlet into the combustion chamber. Note that each OH*-image is normalized to its maximum, which does not allow for a quantitative comparison of the images. Generally, the OH*-chemiluminescence is much weaker for combustion in humid atmosphere.

The OH* distribution of the humid NG-flame (point 2) indicates an axially and radially expanded heat release zone, which moved downstream. The addition of steam leads to a reduced mixture reactivity. In contrast to the H₂-flame, flame speed is insufficient to uphold heat release close to the outlet of the mixing tube.

4.2.2 NO_x-emission. Figure 4 depicts the NO_x-emission as a function of steam ratio for a NG-flame ($\Phi=0.9$) and a H₂-flame ($\Phi=0.7$). Again, all other combustion parameters are otherwise constant ($T_{in}=300^{\circ}\text{C}$, $P_{th}=100\text{ kW}$). The presented points are also shown in the operation envelope (Fig. 2).

NO_x-emissions are in the single-digit NO_x-regime for both fuels under humid conditions. As stated above, steam addition mainly suppresses NO_x-formation via the thermal pathway resulting in overall low NO_x-emission. NO_x-emissions produced from the H₂-flame are lower compared to the NG-flame due to operation at a lower equivalence ratio. Both curves describe a similar trend of decreasing NO_x-emission with increasing steam ratio.

As discussed in the previous section, stable combustion was also realized at dry ($\Omega=0$) conditions. However, the corresponding NO_x-emissions exceed the measurement range of the used NO_x-analyzer (0-120ppm). Note that for demonstration purposes the NO_x-emissions at dry operation are marked in Fig. 2) at 120

ppm even when their true values might be higher.

The comparably high NO_x -emissions at $\Omega=0$ possibly result from insufficient mixing of fuel and air. As mentioned already, under humid conditions fuel/air unmixedness becomes less relevant. However, for increasing steam ratio the NO_x -emissions follow a linear trend in the applied logarithmic scale. NO_x -emissions at $\Omega=0$ can not be extrapolated from this trend. This might indicate that the flame undergoes a transformation which can not be assessed from the presented data. Unfortunately, due to the rig limitations described above, the test rig can not be operated in the region of $0 < \Omega < \sim 0.1$.

In summary, under humid conditions, the Double Swirler concept shows an excellent performance with respect to NO_x -emissions. However, the very high NO_x -emissions for dry combustion exclude standard operation at this condition. Nevertheless, due to the given flame stability at $\Omega=0$, the burner could be operated dry over short times, e.g. for start-up when steam is not available or fuel-switching processes. Also, the emissions behaviour at dry combustion needs to be further analyzed at lower equivalence ratios.

The current work features tests only at atmospheric pressure conditions. Generally, higher NO_x emission are expected at elevated pressure and otherwise equal operation parameters. Stathopoulos et al. [31] investigated the effect of pressure and steam ratio on NO_x emission for a swirl-stabilized combustion system fired with $\text{NG}/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{air}$ and $\text{NG}/\text{H}_2/\text{H}_2\text{O}/\text{air}$. They showed, that in the absence of steam NO_x emission increase strongly with increasing pressure. However, NO_x emission generated at a given pressure are mitigated when increasing the steam ratio. Already for a steam ratio of $\Omega=0.2$ NO_x emission are well within the single-digit region for a pressure of 9 bar even at adiabatic flame temperatures of $T_{ad} > 2000\text{K}$.

The NO_x formation pathways and the resulting pressure scaling are different for MILD conditions [32] than for lean premixed operation [33]. With increasing steam ratio Ω the contribution of thermal NO_x decreases while that of other pathways like N_2O , N_2H or "prompt" is increasing. Since the thermal NO_x pressure scaling is strongest and usually dominating all other paths, a reduction of thermal NO_x formation can explain low NO_x emission even at elevated pressure conditions for MILD conditions.

The design operation range of the here demonstrated burner concept is similar to that presented in [31]. Thus, the NO_x increase for humid operation due to pressure elevation is expected to be less severe than under dry condition.

4.2.3 Pressure loss. The pressure losses over the fuel and steam lines ($\Delta p_{\text{fuel}\&\text{steam}}$) as well as the air line (Δp_{air}) were analyzed for the same operating points as in the previous section. Due to the Double Swirler arrangement, the pressure loss must be computed for the upstream (us) and downstream (ds) swirler separately. The static pressure is measured in the fuel plenum (inlet of the us-swirler), the air plenum (inlet of the ds-swirler) and in the combustion chamber (CC). Therefore, both pressure losses ($\Delta p_{\text{fuel}\&\text{steam}}$) and (Δp_{air}) are composed of the actual pressure loss over the respective swirler ($\Delta p_{\text{us-Swirler}}$, $\Delta p_{\text{ds-Swirler}}$) and a shared pressure loss resulting from the mixing tube (MT) and the flame region (Δp_{MT}).

$$\Delta p_{\text{fuel}\&\text{steam}} = \Delta p_{\text{us-Swirler}} + \Delta p_{\text{MT}} \quad (4)$$

$$\Delta p_{\text{air}} = \Delta p_{\text{ds-Swirler}} + \Delta p_{\text{MT}} \quad (5)$$

In Fig. 5, the pressure loss for the fuel and steam line $\Delta p_{\text{fuel}\&\text{steam}}$ (x-markers) for both the H_2 and NG -flame is continuously increasing from 1% to 3% of the operation pressure with increasing steam ratio. Since steam is supplied only through the us-swirler, at $\Omega=0$ the pressure loss results from the fuel flow and the shared pressure loss Δp_{MT} .

The pressure loss over the downstream swirler lies in the range of 2% to 3% over the presented steam range. From right to left, the pressure loss over the air line Δp_{air} slightly decreases with decreasing steam ratio. Since the equivalence ratio and thermal power, and thus air flow, are kept constant, the change in pressure loss can be ascribed to the decreasing shared pressure loss Δp_{MT} due to decreasing steam flow. For lower values of steam ratio, however, the pressure loss in the air line is increasing with decreasing steam ratio up to its maximum at $\Omega=0$. This behaviour can be explained by altering the flame position. Reducing the steam content increases the mixture's reactivity and flame speed, which causes the flame root to move closer to, or even slightly inside, the mixing tube outlet. Consequently, the outlet is partly blocked by the flame, which causes an increasing pressure loss.

4.3 Evaluation of the pressure loss coefficient ζ

The pressure loss coefficients ζ_i are computed for all relevant components to derive a comparison of the demonstrated Double Swirler concept to existing engines.

As described above, the elements mainly responsible for the pressure loss in the system are the us-swirler (ζ_{us}), the ds-swirler (ζ_{ds}) and the mixing tube and area expansion (ζ_{MT}). Pressure loss in the system is thus described as

$$\Delta p_{\text{air}} = p_{\text{airPlenum}} - p_{\text{CC}} \quad (6)$$

$$= 0.5\zeta_{\text{ds}}\rho_{\text{ds}}u_{\text{ds}}^2 + 0.5\zeta_{\text{MT}}\rho_{\text{MT}}u_{\text{MT}}^2$$

$$\Delta p_{\text{fuel}\&\text{steam}} = p_{\text{fuelPlenum}} - p_{\text{CC}} \quad (7)$$

$$= 0.5\zeta_{\text{us}}\rho_{\text{us}}u_{\text{us}}^2 + 0.5\zeta_{\text{MT}}\rho_{\text{MT}}u_{\text{MT}}^2$$

with the mean axial velocity u , density ρ and pressure loss coefficient ζ . Note that the pressure loss in the mixing tube affects both the pressure loss of the fuel line and the air line.

By assuming constant pressure loss coefficients ζ_i , the pressure loss becomes a linear function of the flow's volume-specific kinetic energy $\rho u^2 \propto \frac{\dot{m}^2}{\rho}$. Inserting the measured mass flowrates and pressure losses, and density from Cantera [23] Ideal gas computation based on measured composition and temperature, into Eq. 6 and 7 yields a system of linear equations, which was solved for ζ_{us} , ζ_{ds} and ζ_{MT} applying MATLAB's least-square solution. The resulting values are presented in Table 2

If the entire (volume-specific pressure) energy is converted into flow in axial direction, pressure loss coefficient yields $\zeta=1$. Loss in the system (friction, geometry variation) increases the required pressure to drive the flow. The creation of swirling flows, where flow velocities in non-axial direction take an

important share, contributes significantly to the pressure loss. Therefore, the swirl magnitude is reflected by an increased pressure loss coefficient.

As expected, the pressure loss coefficient for the mixing tube ζ_{MT} is close to 1, since only the flame region is the main driver for pressure loss.

TABLE 2: BEST-FIT PRESSURE LOSS COEFFICIENTS FOR FUEL LINE, AIR LINE AND MIXING TUBE

Pressure loss coefficient	Value
ζ_{us}	5.0
ζ_{ds}	2.5
ζ_{MT}	1.2

The pressure loss coefficient of the air ds-swirler ζ_{ds} is comparable to that of the AEV-burner [34]. Since the flow area of the us-swirler for steam and fuel is smaller compared to that of the ds-swirler, but flowrates through the swirlers are comparable under humid conditions, ζ_{us} is larger than ζ_{ds} .

4.4 H₂/NG FUEL SWITCH

In the following sub-sections, the combustor’s fuel-flexibility is demonstrated by a continuous fuel transition from pure H₂ to pure NG and vice-versa. This procedure aims at representing the fuel switch process in an engine. Furthermore, the flame behaviour is analyzed for a stepwise fuel switch with steady-state intermediate points.

4.4.1 Continuous fuel transition. The combustor’s fuel switching capability was assessed with a time-resolved continuous fuel switch. The starting point is a stable H₂ flame at a thermal power of $P_{th}=100\text{kW}$, equivalence ratio of $\Phi=0.7$ and steam ratio of $\Omega=0.2$. The air flow and steam flow are kept constant over the entire switching test to preserve the general structure of the flow field. Both air and steam are preheated to $T_{in}=300^\circ\text{C}$. The transition is presented in Fig. 6. The top plot depicts the fuel’s share in thermal power over the time. The center plot presents the total thermal power and exhaust temperature and the bottom plot the NO_x-emission and exhaust temperature. In the following the switch will be analyzed by dividing it into 6 subpoints.

A stable humid H₂ flame is sustained at point 1, exhibiting an exhaust temperature of 870°C and low NO_x-emissions of around

TABLE 3: OPERATION PARAMETERS DURING SWITCH

	1	2	3	4	5	6
H ₂ (dry mol%)	1	76.4	0	29.6	50.5	1
NG (dry mol%)	0	23.6	1	70.4	49.5	0
Φ	0.70	0.83	0.88	0.98	0.84	0.62
Ω	0.20	0.20	0.21	0.19	0.20	0.19
$T_{exhaust}$ (°C)	862	911	941	989	932	842
T_{ad} (K)	1841	1927	1894	2030	1891	1746

FIGURE 6: CONTINUOUS FUEL SWITCH FROM H₂ TO NG AND BACK OVER TIME (S). $T_{in}=300^\circ\text{C}$, $P_{th}=100\text{ kW}$, $\Omega=0.2$
TOP PLOT: THERMAL POWER (KW) FOR H₂ TO NG-FLAME
CENTER PLOT: LEFT AXIS (-): THERMAL POWER (KW), RIGHT AXIS (-): EXHAUST TEMPERATURE (°C)
BOTTOM PLOT: LEFT AXIS (-): ABSOLUTE NO_x-EMISSION (PPM), RIGHT AXIS (-): EXHAUST TEMPERATURE (°C)

1-2ppm. Subsequently, flowrate of H₂ is reduced while at the same time that of NG is increased. The flowrate of air and steam are showing only minor fluctuations over the switch and can be regarded as constant over the entire time. The objective was to maintain combustion at a constant thermal power. However, due to a delay in the valve control, the fuel flowrate could not be controlled in a perfect continuous manner, which is mainly associated with the NG valve. This results in power fluctuation over the switch of up to $\pm 15\%$ of the base load power. An optimized engine should operate within a smaller tolerance range during the transition. The transition process on a test rig or engine can be improved by optimizing the valve control system in order to predict the power change for a valve command. Further, such an

FIGURE 7: LINE-OF-SIGHT AND TIME-AVERAGED OH*-IMAGES FOR FUEL TRANSITION FROM NG TO H₂, T_{in}=300°C, P_{th}=100 KW, Ω=0.2, Φ=0.8

optimization must account for the delayed actual valve response in the combustor including the pressures and pipe lengths in the fuel distribution system. Such transient studies will be required for much faster and smoother transitions than the one shown here.

At point 2, both fuels contribute equally to the total thermal power. Since air flow is kept constant, switching fuel from H₂ to NG induces an increase in equivalence ratio. Accordingly, the exhaust temperature is increased likewise, which becomes apparent when comparing power and exhaust temperature in the center plot in Fig. 6. The temperature adjustment to the changed operating conditions exhibits only a marginal delay compared to thermal power, owing to the fact that the thermal power is computed from the measured mass flows upstream and the exhaust temperature is measured downstream of the flame. This results in a time gap of approximately 3 s. Moreover, NO_x-emissions follow the same trend as the exhaust temperature. However, the time delay is more distinct and of approximately 13 s. This is due to the longer flow path of the extracted emissions and additional process time of emission analyzer. In a previous study, it was shown that NO_x-emissions in humid NG/H₂/air flames are highly sensitive to the flame temperature and relatively independent of the fuel's composition [18].

A humid NG/air flame is present in point 3. The equivalence ratio increased to Φ=0.88, which results in increased exhaust temperature and NO_x-emission.

FIGURE 8: NO_x-EMISSION OVER H₂ MOL% FOR T_{in}=300°C, P_{th}=100 KW, Ω=0.2, Φ=0.8 (-) AND Φ=0.9 (- -)
LEFT AXIS: NO_x ABSOLUTE AND CORRECTED TO 15%O₂ IN PPM
RIGHT AXIS: NO_x CORRECTED TO 15%O₂ IN G/MJ

The transition from NG back to H₂ follows point 3. In point 4, H₂ is flowing without the NG flowrate being reduced. As a result, the thermal power, exhaust temperature and NO_x-emission exhibit a peak. Clearly, this behaviour can be accounted to the test rig limitation. In a real engine, a smoother transition could be realized, thus avoiding these kind of peaks.

In the next step, the NG flowrate is continuously reduced, increasing the H₂ flowrate likewise. At point 5, again both fuels provide the same thermal power input. Reaching point 6, the flame is fully sustained on H₂, which is also represented in the exhaust temperature and NO_x-emissions.

4.4.2 Stepwise fuel switch. For a better understanding of the flame behaviour during the fuel switch, the transition from a NG to a H₂ flame is performed with intermediate steps. For every intermediate point, all combustion parameters such as fuel flows, temperatures and emissions are steady-state.

Flame image: Figure 7 shows line-of-sight and time-averaged OH* emission normalized to the maximum emission of the presented group. The flow direction is from left to right. As before, the inlet temperature is T_{in}=300°C, thermal power P_{th}=100 kW and steam ratio Ω=0.2. Here, also the equivalence ratio is kept constant over the entire switch at Φ=0.8 to remove the dilution effect on the combustion, thus enabling the analysis of the flame behaviour solely affected by the varying fuel composition. An equivalence ratio close to the stoichiometric resembles operation in humid power cycles.

At 0vol% H₂ a typical V-flame is located in a relatively central position, which radially expands entirely to the combustor walls. With increasing H₂-content, and thus mixture's reactivity, the flame root and main heat release zone move upstream and closer to the burner base plate. Furthermore, the flame becomes axially and radially more compact. This effect leads to increased OH*-presence per volume for increasing the H₂-

content up to 80vol% H₂, where the maximum OH*-emission is reached. By further increasing the H₂-content, and consequently decreasing NG, OH*-intensity decreases slightly. This might be due to NG-flame's higher OH*-emission compared to H₂-flame. There are two reasons for that: Mainly the kinetic pathways to OH*-chemiluminescence differ for both fuel types (CH + O₂ ⇒ versus H + O + M ⇒ [35, 36]) with a much higher luminosity for the hydrocarbons. Further the flame moving back upstream out of view resulting in less light on the camera.

NO_x-emission: In Fig. 8 NO_x emission as a function of H₂ content are presented over the NG/H₂ transition for equivalence ratios of $\Phi=0.8$ and 0.9 ($T_{in}=300^{\circ}\text{C}$, thermal power $P_{th}=100$ kW, steam ratio $\Omega=0.2$). Increasing the H₂-content leads to increasing NO_x-emission. This could be explained with increasing flame temperature. Likewise, $\Phi=0.8$ emits lower NO_x than $\Phi=0.9$. The raw emissions are below 10.1 ppm for all cases (left axis). By correcting the NO_x-emission to 15% O₂ in the exhaust, these values lie between 1 and 3.2 ppm (left axis). The correction to energy according to the procedure described in the Appendix yields values between 1.7-4.0 g(NO₂)/MJ(thermal) (right axis).

While the volume based values (ppm) increase by more than a factor of 2 for increasing the H₂ content from 0 to 100%, the energy weighted values are within 40% (for $\Phi=0.8$) and 15% (for $\Phi=0.9$) over the same range. This indicates the high fuel-flexibility of the Double Swirler burner for this humid combustion system in compliance with emissions regulations.

5. CONCLUSION

In this work, a novel Double Swirler concept for humid and fuel-flexible combustion was introduced. In a first experimental demonstration, it showed a large operation window for H₂, NG and syngas combustion. The NO_x-emission performance was excellent under humid conditions. A continuous fuel transition from 100% H₂ to 100% NG at fairly constant performance on the same combustor was demonstrated within minutes. This demonstrates the capability of the combustion system for safe hydrogen combustion. Additionally, safe operation under dry conditions was demonstrated at higher NO_x-emissions, which can be used for engine start-up without steam. The pressure loss lies well within the required range over the entire operating envelope. For the comparison, NO_x-emissions are quoted based on energy to comply with ongoing recommendation on emission correction.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work was carried out as part of the project "PACS2020" (Eurostars E!114441, Demonstration of Phoenix Advanced Combustion System for the Decarbonised Energy System), and "Bio-FlexGen" (Horizon Europe Grant 101037085, Highly-efficient and flexible integration of biomass and renewable hydrogen for low-cost combined heat and power generation to the energy system). The financing contribution of CINEA, Vinnova, DLR and Phoenix Biopower is therefore gratefully acknowledged. The authors thank David Graham, from Uniper UK for helpful discussions concerning emission calibration and standards.

REFERENCES

- [1] European Commission statement, "The European Green Deal." https://eur-lex.europa.eu/resource.html?uri=cellar:b828d165-1c22-11ea-8c1f-01aa75ed71a1.0002.02/DOC_1&format=PDF, 12 2019. information taken from web on 05.11.2022.
- [2] International Energy Agency, *World Energy Outlook 2019*. 2019.
- [3] ETN Global, "Hydrogen Gas Turbines – The Path to a Zero Emissions Gas Turbine." <https://etn.global/wp-content/uploads/2020/01/ETN-Hydrogen-Gas-Turbines-report.pdf>, 2020. White Paper, ETN Global, Brussels, Belgium.
- [4] T. Lieuwen, V. McDonell, E. Petersen, and D. Santavicca, "Fuel Flexibility Influences on Premixed Combustor Blowout, Flashback, Autoignition, and Stability," *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 130, 01 2008. 011506.
- [5] J. Tober, "Boundary layer flashback prediction of a low emissions full hydrogen burner for gas turbine applications," Master's thesis, Delft University of Technology, 2019.
- [6] C. Dong, Q. Zhou, X. Zhang, Q. Zhao, T. Xu, and S. Hui, "Experimental study on the laminar flame speed of hydrogen/natural gas/air mixtures," *Frontiers of Chemical Engineering in China*, vol. 4, pp. 417–422, 12 2010.
- [7] B. Mohammad, N. Magina, B. Volk, and K. Mcmanus, "Impact of High Hydrogen Operation on Combustor Performance," *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo*, 06 2022.
- [8] M. Brower, E. L. Petersen, W. Metcalfe, H. J. Curran, M. Furi, G. Bourque, N. Aluri, and F. Güthe, "Ignition Delay Time and Laminar Flame Speed Calculations for Natural Gas/Hydrogen Blends at Elevated Pressures," *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 135, 01 2013. 021504.
- [9] E. Petersen, J. Hall, S. Smith, J. de Vries, A. Amadio, and M. Crofton, "Ignition of Lean Methane-Based Fuel Blends at Gas Turbine Pressures," *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 129, 10 2007.
- [10] B. Witzel, D. Moëll, N. Parsania, E. Yilmaz, and M. Koenig, "Development of a Fuel Flexible H₂-Natural Gas Gas Turbine Combustion Technology Platform," *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo*, 06 2022.
- [11] W. Krebs, A. Schulz, B. Witzel, C. Johnson, W. Laster, J. Pent, R. Schilp, S. Wasif, and A. Weaver, "Advanced Combustion System for High Efficiency (ACE) of the new SGT5/6-9000HL Gas Turbine," *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo*, 06 2022.
- [12] B. Ćosić, D. Waßmer, D. Kluß, A. Jaeschke, T. Reichel, and C. Paschereit, "Experimental and Numerical Advancement of the MGT Combustor towards Higher Hydrogen Capabilities," *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo*, 06 2022.
- [13] A. Horikawa, K. Okada, M. Yamaguchi, S. Aoki, M. Wirsum, H. H.-W. Funke, and K. Kusterer, "Combustor Development and Engine Demonstration of Micro-Mix Hydrogen Combustion Applied to M1A-17 Gas Turbine," vol. Volume 3B: Combustion, Fuels, and Emissions of *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, 06 2021. V03BT04A014.

- [14] S. Göke, *Ultra wet combustion: an experimental and numerical study*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität Berlin, 2012.
- [15] A. Cavaliere and M. de Joannon, “Mild Combustion,” *Progress in Energy and Combustion Science*, vol. 30, no. 4, pp. 329–366, 2004.
- [16] R. Palulli, S. Dybe, K. Zhang, F. Güthe, R. Alemela, C. Paschereit, and C. Duwig, “Characterisation of non-premixed, swirl-stabilized, wet hydrogen/air flame using large eddy simulation,” *Submitted to Fuel*, 02 2023.
- [17] T. Tanneberger, *Investigation of zero-emission hydrogen oxyfuel flames*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität Berlin, 2020.
- [18] S. Dybe, R. Bluemner, K. Zhang, S. Schimek, C. Duwig, P. Stathopoulos, C. Paschereit, and M. Bartlett, “Design and Experimental Characterization of a Swirl-Stabilized Combustor for Low Calorific Value Gaseous Fuels,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 144, 01 2021.
- [19] S. Dybe, F. Güthe, M. Bartlett, P. Stathopoulos, and C. O. Paschereit, “Experimental Characterization of the Combustion in Fuel Flexible Humid Power Cycles,” *Proceedings of ASME Turbo Expo*, 2021. V03AT04A012.
- [20] S. Dybe, M. Bartlett, J. Pålsson, and P. Stathopoulos, “Top-Cycle: A Novel High Performance and Fuel Flexible Gas Turbine Cycle,” *Sustainability*, vol. 13, no. 2, 2021.
- [21] K. Göckeler, *Influence of steam dilution and hydrogen enrichment on laminar premixed methane flames*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität Berlin, 2015.
- [22] T. Reichel, *Flasback prevention in lean-premixed hydrogen combustion Dissertation*. PhD thesis, Technische Universität Berlin, 2012.
- [23] <https://cantera.org/>. information taken from web on 24.02.2023.
- [24] G. Smith, Y. Tao, and H. Wang, “Foundational Fuel Chemistry Model Version 1.0 (FFCM-1).” <https://web.stanford.edu/group/haiwanglab/FFCM1/pages/download.html>, 2016. information taken from web on 24.02.2023.
- [25] A. Eroglu, J. Larfeldt, E. V. Klapdor, E. Yilmaz, V. N. Prasad, B. Prade, B. Witzel, and M. Koenig, “Hydrogen Capabilities of Siemens Energy Gas Turbines, an OEM Perspective,” *10th International Gas Turbine Conference*, vol. 141, 10 2021.
- [26] C. M. Douglas, S. L. Shaw, T. D. Martz, R. C. Steele, D. R. Noble, B. L. Emerson, and T. C. Lieuwen, “Pollutant Emissions Reporting and Performance Considerations for Hydrogen–Hydrocarbon Fuels in Gas Turbines,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 144, 07 2022. 091003.
- [27] Various authors, “Addressing the Combustion Challenges of Hydrogen Addition to Natural Gas.”
- [28] N. Garan, S. Dybe, C. O. Paschereit, and N. Djordjevic, “Consistent emission correction factors applicable to novel energy carriers and conversion concepts,” *Fuel*, vol. 341, p. 127658, 2023.
- [29] H. Zhen, C. Leung, and C. Cheung, “Effects of hydrogen addition on the characteristics of a biogas diffusion flame,” *International journal of hydrogen energy*, vol. 38, no. 16, pp. 6874–6881, 2013.
- [30] R. Schefer, W. Kulatilaka, B. Patterson, and T. Settersten, “Visible emission of hydrogen flames,” *Combustion and Flame*, vol. 156, no. 6, pp. 1234–1241, 2009.
- [31] P. Stathopoulos, P. Kuhn, J. Peukert, T. Tanneberger, S. Terhaar, C. Paschereit, C. Schmalhofer, P. Griebel, and M. Aigner, “Emissions of a Wet Premixed Flame of Natural Gas and a Mixture With Hydrogen at High Pressure,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 139, 09 2016.
- [32] F. Güthe, M. de la Cruz Garcíá, and A. Burdet, “Flue Gas Recirculation in Gas Turbine: Investigation of Combustion Reactivity and NOX Emission,” *Turbo Expo: Power for Land, Sea, and Air*, vol. Volume 2: Combustion, Fuels and Emissions, pp. 179–191, 06 2009.
- [33] F. Biagioli and F. Güthe, “Effect of pressure and fuel–air unmixedness on NOx emissions from industrial gas turbine burners,” *Combustion and Flame*, vol. 151, pp. 274–288, 10 2007.
- [34] M. Zajadatz, F. Güthe, E. Freitag, T. Ferreira-Providakis, T. Wind, F. Magni, and J. Goldmeer, “Extended Range of Fuel Capability for GT13E2 AEV Burner with Liquid and Gaseous Fuels,” *Journal of Engineering for Gas Turbines and Power*, vol. 141, 08 2018.
- [35] T. Kathrotia, M. Fikri, M. Bozkurt, M. Hartmann, U. Riedel, and C. Schulz, “Study of the H+O+M reaction forming OH*: Kinetics of OH chemiluminescence in hydrogen combustion systems,” *Combustion and Flame*, vol. 157, no. 7, pp. 1261–1273, 2010.
- [36] A. G. Gaydon, *The Spectroscopy of Flames*. 1974.

APPENDIX A. FUEL FACTOR

For a general fuel (possibly composed of several fuel components) of composition $C_nH_mO_lN_p$ the stoichiometric equation (introducing stoichiometric factors) reads like this:

The fuel volume per thermal energy is the inverse of the volumetric heating value, which can be determined for a given fuel composition as:

$$V_{fuel} = \frac{1}{LHV_V} = \frac{1}{LHV_m \cdot \rho_{fuel}} \quad (9)$$

The fuel factor, $S[\frac{m^3}{MJ}]$ resembles the volume of the exhaust flow after combustion.

$$S = V_{CO_2} + V_{O_2} + V_{N_2, inerts} + V_{N_2, react} \quad (10)$$

Air is composed of O_2 (21%) and N_2 (79%), or more generally: The oxygen content of the oxidiser is diluted by inerts with $x_{O_2, ox, dry}$ (i.e. 0.2095 for air) and $x_{N_2, inerts} = 1 - x_{O_2, ox, dry}$:

$$\frac{x_{N_2, inerts}}{x_{O_2, ox, dry}} = \frac{1 - x_{O_2, ox, dry}}{x_{O_2, ox, dry}} = \frac{1}{x_{O_2, ox, dry}} - 1 \quad (11)$$

i.e. 3.79 for air.

The air excess number $\lambda = 1/\phi$ is defined as the ratio of available to consumed oxidant:

$$\lambda = \frac{x_{O_2,ox,dry}}{x_{O_2,exh}} - x_{O_2,exh} \quad (12)$$

$$\Rightarrow x_{O_2,exh} = x_{O_2,ox,dry} \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{\lambda}\right) \quad (13)$$

With this fuel factor can be expressed like for every fuel composition, oxidised and stoichiometry from equation (10):

$$S = \frac{n + \frac{p}{2} + \nu_{stoich} \cdot (\lambda - 1) + \left(\frac{1}{x_{O_2,ox,dry}} - 1\right) \cdot \lambda}{LHV_V} \quad (14)$$

For stoichiometric conditions $\lambda=1$ or $O_{2,exh}=0$ the values given in the ISO-12952 standard can be reproduced and determined

accurately for any given composition and just molecular properties lie stoichiometry and heating value:

$$S = \frac{n + \frac{p}{2} + \nu_{stoich} \cdot \frac{1}{x_{O_2,ox,dry}-1}}{LHV_V} \quad (15)$$

Correction to 15% O₂ can be done simply:

$$S_{@15\%O_2} = \frac{n + \frac{p}{2} + \nu_{stoich} \cdot \frac{1}{x_{O_2,ox,dry}-1}}{LHV_V} \cdot \frac{0.2095 - 0.0}{0.2095 - 0.15} \quad (16)$$

The measured emission expressed in mass (for NO_x as g(NO₂)) per volume [$\frac{mg}{Nm^3}$] corrected to 15% O₂ can be combined with the fuel factor $S[\frac{m^3}{MJ}]$ to calculate the emissions corrected to energy units of [$\frac{mg}{MJ}$] (net thermal input) for alternative fuels as practical and reasonable comparison of combustor performance and environmental impact.